

FEATURES OF GIARDIASIS ACCOMPANIED BY ALLERGIC SYMPTOMS IN CHILDREN

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Abstract

According to official WHO statistics, giardiasis ranks third in the structure of childhood parasitic diseases. Constant parasitism of the Giardia pathogen in the small and large intestines leads to disruption of the functional state of the intestinal mucosa and the progression of a nonspecific clinical picture of the disease. On the other hand, with giardiasis, the occurrence of an inadequate immune response to microorganisms leads to skin itching, allergic reactions of various forms and localization on the skin of the face and body. In most cases, the clinical signs of giardiasis in children are masked under various clinical variants of other gastroenterological pathologies and symptoms of allergic diseases, which creates some difficulties in clarifying the diagnosis. For this reason, giardiasis continues to remain one of the pressing medical and social problems facing pediatricians. The study we presented presents the results of a study of the clinical signs and characteristics of the course of giardiasis in 18 children aged 3 to 15 years, accompanied by allergic symptoms

Keywords. children, giardiasis, complaints, clinic, treatment, prevention.

Introduction. For many years, parasitic diseases occupy one of the leading places in the structure of general morbidity of the population, and one of the main places among these diseases belongs to giardiasis, which is considered one of the most common parasitic infections [1,7]. According to official WHO statistics, giardiasis ranks third in the structure of childhood parasitic diseases (about 20-25%) [7]. These unicellular primitive microorganisms (*Lamblia intestinalis*, or *Giardia Lamblia*) measuring 10-18 microns parasitize primarily in the small intestine. Giardiasis, considered the brightest representative of the simplest invasions, occurs not only in the form of latent parasite carriage, but also in a manifest form with predominant damage to the small intestine. Despite the fact that giardiasis infection occurs primarily through food and water contaminated with Giardia cysts, it can also be transmitted from person to person (“*from hand to hand*”) when children in preschool institutions use shared utensils [2,7]. There are vegetative and cystic forms of pathogenic microorganisms. While the upper parts of the small intestine are parasitized by the vegetative form of Giardia, which is very sensitive to external environmental factors, cystic (spore) forms of the pathogen (which can maintain their vital activity for up to 3 months) settle in the upper parts of the small intestine, in the large intestine and are excreted from the body in feces. With giardiasis, constant parasitism of the pathogen in the small and large intestines leads to disruption of the functional state of the intestinal mucosa and progression of the nonspecific clinical picture of the disease. With giardiasis in children, in addition to dysfunction of the office, there is also an inadequate immune response against microorganisms, which leads to allergic reactions in the form of itchy skin, various forms and localized elements of a rash on the skin of the face and body. The difficulties in identifying giardiasis in children lie precisely in the fact that its clinical signs are disguised as various clinical variants of other gastroenterological pathologies

(functional disorders of the gastrointestinal tract, syndrome of excessive growth of microflora in the small intestine, malabsorption syndrome, etc.) and sometimes, as already mentioned above, it is similar to the clinic of allergic diseases (recurrent urticaria, atopic dermatitis, gastrointestinal form of food allergy), combined with symptoms [8,9]. It has been established that Giardia has a cytotoxic effect on the intestinal epithelium, causing various morphological and biochemical changes similar to food allergies. In various literary sources, giardiasis is characterized by persistent skin itching, urticaria, bronchial asthma, allergic bronchitis, etc. Information about clinical forms has been published [2-4]. Due to the widespread prevalence of allergic diseases, allergies continue to be one of the most pressing medical and social problems facing pediatricians. It should be borne in mind that any clinical symptoms of allergic diseases, such as atopic dermatitis, allergic rhinitis, bronchial asthma, can be aggravated by the activity of parasites, especially Giardia, living in the human body, and the severity of the allergic process depends on the number of Giardia antigens entering the body, the localization of the parasite and its contact with human tissues [4,7].

Goal of the work. Study features of giardiasis accompanied by allergic symptoms in children.

Material and methods. The study was conducted on 64 children with giardiasis aged 3 to 15 years, of which 18 (28.1%) had giardiasis accompanied by allergic reactions. To achieve this goal, further studies were carried out on these 18 children to study clinical signs. The diagnosis of the disease was established on the basis of the results of coproovoscopy and serological testing carried out against the background of clinical symptoms, as well as by ELISA to detect antibodies to Giardia antigens (IgM and IgG). All children underwent a general blood test.

Results. in 18 children (11 girls, 7 boys) with giardiasis included in the survey, allergic symptoms were more common (n=11; 61.1%) in school-age children. In

10 cases (55.6% of the total number of those examined), the patients were aged 6-12 years, in 1 case (5.6%) - 15 years. Allergic reactions were observed in the remaining 7 (38.9%) preschool children: 1 (5.6%) case - 3 years; 6 (33.3%) cases - in children aged 3-7 years. Among patients with giardiasis with allergic reactions, children who applied to organized child care institutions predominated (n=16; 88.9%), 2 (11.1%) patients were children left at home. The reasons for testing for giardiasis were different. Thus, in 17 (94.4%) of 18 patients, the reason for the examination was clinical complaints and symptoms, and only in 1 (5.6%) case - contact with giardiasis in the family. At the same time, the main complaints in 8 (44.4%) patients were pain in the epigastric region, in 4 (22.2%) patients - stool discharge, in 3 (16.7%) patients - teeth grinding in a child at night. Symptoms such as loss of appetite (n=3; 16.7%), nausea (n=2; 11.1%) and alopecia (n=1; 5.6%) with giardiasis infestation with allergic symptoms were rarely and rarely recorded. At the time of collecting the anamnesis, all children (n=18) had bad habits. In most cases, children do not comply with hygiene rules, that is, not washing their hands (n=9; 50%), onychophagy eating thorns (n=5; 27.8%), geophagy eating soil (n=2; 11.1%), as well as close contact of some children with non-dewormed domestic animals: with dogs - n=4 (22.2%); in cats - n=5 (27.8%) facts were identified. Ultrasound of the abdominal organs in these children revealed some changes in the pancreas, including: in 8 (44.4%) patients, reactive changes in the pancreas; in 5 (27.8%) patients there were signs of biliary dyskinesia. Reactive changes in the liver were registered in 2 patients (11.1%), and splenomegaly and lymphadenitis - in 1 patient (5.6%) each. It should be noted that in 1 (5.6%) patient, ultrasound of the abdominal organs did not reveal any pathology. It is known that laboratory examination of biological material, along with complaints and clinical signs, is of great importance in establishing the final diagnosis of giardiasis. For this purpose, all children (n=18) had positive results of laboratory tests (coproscopic and serological studies of biological material (stool), as well as IFA conducted to detect *Giardia* antigens). With the exception of mild leukocytosis, eosinophilia and anemia, recorded in 4 (22.2%) patients during a general blood test, in the majority of patients (n=14; 77.8%) no noticeable changes were recorded. All patients (n=18) were prescribed drug therapy using antiparasitic drugs. Of these, 15 (83.3%) patients over the age of 6 years received nifuratel in acceptable doses (15 mg/kg twice a day for 7 days), and 3 (16.7%) patients received metronidazole for 5 days (3-5 days). years - 0.25 g, 0.375 g at 6-10 years and 0.50 g at 11-15 years). After the end of treatment, despite the negative results obtained during a 2-fold control study of biological material in all children, complete recovery with the disappearance of clinical symptoms was recorded in 85% of patients immediately after treatment. At this stage, although 20% of children retain some symptoms characteristic of *Giardia*, a few days after stopping the drug, complete recovery is recorded with the disappearance of these symptoms.

Conclusion. Based on the latest research results, we can conclude that giardiasis infection, accompanied by allergic symptoms, is more common in school-age children than in preschool children. Characteristic symptoms of the disease include pain in the epigastric region, loose stools and grinding of teeth during night sleep. Among the causes of the development of the disease, in addition to such bad habits as poor personal hygiene and nail biting, close contact with pets that have not been dewormed can play an important role. Complete recovery after treatment with nifuratel and metronidazole occurs in most cases immediately after the end of treatment and in rare cases several days after stopping the drug.

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